

Research article

New record of *Orientus ishidae* (Matsumura, 1902) (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) in Bulgaria with notes on the distribution of *Acanalonia conica* (Say, 1830) (Hemiptera: Acanaloniidae)

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Abstract: *Orientus ishidae* (Matsumura, 1902), a leafhopper species native to East Asia, has been increasingly reported in Europe due to its potential role as a vector of phytoplasmas affecting agricultural crops. In this study, we present the first confirmed record of *O. ishidae* in Bulgaria, collected from Varna town during field surveys in 2024. The occurrence of *O. ishidae* in Bulgaria raises concerns about its potential impact on the country's agriculture, particularly grapevines and fruit crops, which are vulnerable to the phytoplasma diseases vectored by this species. A new distribution records of *Acanalonia conica* (Say, 1830), previously known only from the most southeastern parts of the country, is indicating that the species established in the north-east and west parts. These records expand the known distribution of both species, *O. ishidae* and *A. conica* in Europe, highlighting the need for continued monitoring and management strategies.

Keywords: *Acanalonia conica*, Acanaloniidae, Bulgaria, Cicadellidae, Hemiptera, invasive species, *Orientus ishidae*, phytoplasma vector

Introduction

The establishment and spread of non-native insect species pose a significant challenge to local ecosystems due the potential effects on biodiversity and agricultural practices (Jeschke et al., 2014). Among such insects, *Orientus ishidae* (Matsumura, 1902) (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae), commonly known as the mosaic leafhopper or Japanese leafhopper has gained attention due to its rapid spread across Europe. *Orientus* DeLong, 1938 is a small genus of leafhoppers containing only two species: *Orientus amurensis* Guglielmino, 2005 distributed in China and the Russian Far East, and *Orientus ishidae*. *Orientus ishidae* is native to Japan where it was originally described (Matsumura, 1902; Hayashi et al., 2016) and China (Zhang, 2014), besides the species has become established in various regions of

Europe and North America (EPPO, 2024). The previous records of *O. ishidae* from the Russian Far East as well as from the Korean Peninsula and the Philippines need confirmation (Guglielmino, 2005). The first report of the species in Europe was in the early 2000s, when it was documented from Switzerland (Günthart & Mühlethaler, 2002), Germany (Nickel & Remane, 2003) and Italy (Guglielmino, 2005) also. Since then, it has spread widely, with confirmed records in Slovenia (Seljak, 2004), Czech Republic (Malenovský & Lauterer, 2006) and Austria (Holzinger, 2009). More recently, it has been reported in United Kingdom (Frith, 2012), France (Callot & Brua, 2013) including Corsica (Albre & Gibernau, 2019), Hungary (Koczor et al., 2013), Netherlands (Den Bieman & Van Klink, 2015), Poland (Klejdzysz et al., 2017), Romania (Chireceanu et al., 2017), Belgium (Lock, 2019), Serbia (Šćiban &

Fig. 1. Habitus photograph of *Orientus ishidae* female.

Kosovac, 2020) and Portugal (Grosso-Silva, 2022), suggesting a pattern of migration radiating toward south-central Europe. In North America this species is distributed in several states of USA (Hamilton, 1983) and Canada (George, 1959; Hamilton, 1983, 1985). The species is arboreal, broadly polyphagous organism (Parise, 2017; Chireceanu et al., 2017). This species has proven highly adaptable to temperate European climates and various host plants, leading to concerns about its impact on local ecosystems and agriculture, as it is a potential vector for plant pathogens, including flavescence dorée type of phytoplasma disease (Mehle et al., 2010, 2011; Trivellone et al., 2015; Chireceanu et al., 2017).

The planthopper *Acanalonia conica* (Say, 1830), native to North America, has also been expanding its range within Europe. Known for its distinctive conical shape and vibrant green coloration, *A. conica* was firstly recorded in Europe in Italy in 2004 (D'Urso & Uliana, 2006). Over the following years, it has spread to other Mediterranean and Central European countries (Cojocariu & Crişmaru, 2023). Recently, it was

Fig. 2. The collecting site of the species in Varna.

recorded in Bulgaria for the first time (Gjonov et al., 2023). The adaptability of the species to various habitats and climate conditions in Europe has enabled it to expand further north, with recent sightings in the Netherlands and Belgium. Although its ecological im-

Fig. 3. Habitus photograph of *Acanalonia conica* female.

pact is not fully understood, the presence of *A. conica* in various European habitats, including urban areas and agricultural landscapes, suggests its potential to disrupt local biodiversity and act as a minor agricultural pest (Cojocariu & Crîșmaru, 2023).

This study documents the first confirmed presence of *O. ishidae* in Varna, Bulgaria, expanding the known European distribution of this species into Southeastern Europe. Additionally, we present a new records of *A. conica* in the same locality and in Sofia, supporting its ongoing spread within Europe. These findings underscore the need for monitoring non-native Hemiptera in Bulgaria and contribute to understanding the geographic expansion of both species across the continent.

Materials and methods

Fieldwork was conducted in Bulgaria, Varna, on 13 July and in Sofia on 12 September 2024. Specimens were collected by hand on tree canopies and photographed in situ. Specimens were examined under Euromex DZ.1100 stereomicroscope for morphological identification. Identification was based on the morphological keys provided by Biedermann &

Niedringhaus (2009). The collected material was dry-mounted and deposited in the Zoological Collection of Sofia University (BFUS). The specimens were photographed using a Canon 70D DSLR camera with a Canon MP-E 65mm macro lens and a Yongnuo YN-24EX macro flash, to document the morphology and habitat of the species. Distribution map for both species were created using QGIS.

Results

Superfamily Membracoidea Rafinesque, 1815
Family Cicadellidae Latreille, 1825
Subfamily Deltocephalinae Fieber, 1869
Tribe Athysanini Van Duzee, 1892
Genus *Orientus* DeLong, 1938

Orientus ishidae (Matsumura, 1902) (Fig. 1)

Bulgaria: 2 ♂♂ (from BFUS-I-IG030143 to BFUS-I-IG030144), 5 ♀♀ (from BFUS-I-IG030145 to BFUS-I-IG030149), Varna, 43°13'50"N 27°51'54"E, 75 m a.s.l., 13.VII.2024, on *Celtis australis* Linnaeus, 1753 (Rosales: Cannabaceae) (Fig. 2), leg. I. Gjonov & R. Angelova.

Fig. 4. Distribution map of *O. ishidae* and *A. conica* in Bulgaria, including the new Varna record.

Superfamily Fulgoroidea Latreille, 1807
Family Acanaloniidae Amyot & Serville, 1843
Genus *Acanalonia* Spinola, 1839

Acanalonia conica (Say, 1830) (Fig. 3)

Bulgaria: 7 ♂♂ (from BFUS-I-IG030150 to BFUS-I-IG030156), 3 ♀♀ (from BFUS-I-IG030157 to BFUS-I-IG030159), Varna, 43°13'50"N 27°51'54"E, 75 m a.s.l., 13.VII.2024, on various tree canopies (Fig. 2), leg. I. Gjonov & R. Angelova; 1 ♀ (BFUS-I-IG030160), Sofia, 42°41'16"N 23°19'15"E, 557 m a.s.l., 12.IX.2024, leg. R. Angelova.

Discussion

This study provides the first confirmed record of *Orientus ishidae* in Bulgaria (Fig. 4), expanding its known range in Europe. The presence of the species in the country raises concerns about its potential role

in the transmission of phytoplasmas. The identification of *O. ishidae* highlights the importance of early detection and monitoring efforts for invasive species. The establishment of the species on *Celtis australis* represents a further addition to the extensive list of potential host plants.

Given the potential agricultural and ecological impact of *O. ishidae* as a vector of phytoplasmas, particularly in grapevines, further studies are required to monitor the spread of this species in Bulgaria. Surveillance programs should focus on both insect populations and plant hosts to assess the risk of phytoplasma transmission and implement appropriate management strategies.

The detection of *A. conica* in Varna and Sofia (Fig. 3) provides new information on its distribution range, highlighting its adaptability to diverse climates and habitats. Both species are considered potential vectors for plant pathogens, raising concerns about the ecological and agricultural impacts of their spread.

Acknowledgments

This study was partly supported by the National Science Fund of the Republic of Bulgaria, grant No. KP-06-N81/4 from 04.12.2024. We would like to express our gratitude to Bilyana Greenish for alerting us to the presence of *Orientus ishidae* in Varna. We are grateful to Nikolay Simov (National Museum of Natural History, Sofia, Bulgaria) and Bence Schlitt (Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, Hungary) for their contributions to the improvement of the manuscript.

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